

Perspectives of Managing Talent in Indonesia: Challenges and Strategy

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Abstract

Talent management has been proven to be one of the key elements for organization to gain its competitive advantage. An effective talent management process: from attracting, developing, and retaining talent; will increase the employees' commitment and satisfaction that lead to employees' engagement. There has been a shift in perspective regarding talent management, one of which was caused by the Covid-19 pandemic. The impact of the pandemic still occurs and will continue to influence human life, especially companies which of course must survive in this very dynamic conditions. Organizations face various challenges, especially in terms of how to manage their talent management. This paper aims to explore the conditions of talent management in Indonesian, describes several challenges which could influence the talent management in Indonesia, and strategy executions to build the global talent pipeline in Indonesia.

Keywords: *challenges, perspectives, strategy, talent management*